

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE IDEA OF FUSIONISM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' EDUCATIONAL PRACTICE IN GEOMETRY

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the importance of the ideas of fusionism in the development of students' learning practice, the main tasks of teaching geometry in schools, and also the importance of the idea of fusionism in the development of students' spatial representation in the school geometry course.*

Keywords: *teaching geometry, fusionism, planimetry, stereometry, spatial representation, triangle, square, rectangle, circle, cube, pyramid, parallelepiped, sphere.*

Introduction

In modern conditions, the main pedagogical ideas are the ideas of humanization, humanitarianization and democratization, which form the basis of new educational priorities. During the learning process, students must acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in various activities. It can be concluded that all this has a huge impact on human development. The activities of both the teacher and students are aimed primarily at mastering the educational material. The process of mastering is carried out in stages. So first comes the perception of information, then its comprehension. At the next stage of receiving information, it is understood, after which it begins to be generalized, then consolidated, and finally applied. It is important to remember that all these stages are interconnected, although sometimes they are carried out in a different sequence. In this regard, the idea of fusionism in the study of geometry plays an important role.

The term fusionism comes from the Latin word fusio – fusion. This is what they called the joint teaching of various school subjects in the 19th century, for example, physics and mathematics, chemistry and biology. Fusionism was also called the combined teaching of several sections of mathematics: algebra and geometry; geometry and arithmetic; finally, plane geometry and stereometry.

Many scientists, such as V.A. Gusev, P.M. Erdniev, G. Freudenthal, N.S. Podkhodova, G.A. Klekovkin, N.E. Maryukova, and B.P. Erdniev, speak of the fusionist approach to presenting the school geometry course as one of the most effective. In particular, B.P. Erdniev rightly states in his article: “It is didactically appropriate to offer students to simultaneously observe pairs of objects already in primary school: a sphere and a circle, a sphere and a circumference, remembering that in the ontogenesis of thinking it was the “volumetric” that preceded the “flat” and that the most instructive thing in geometry is the derivation of the planimetric from the stereometric.”

Methods

The main objectives of teaching geometry in general schools are:

- 1) studying spatial forms;
- 2) developing spatial imagination;
- 3) cultivating correct logical thinking;

4) instilling practical skills, including the ability to solve various geometric problems of a theoretical nature, as well as the ability to apply one's knowledge to solving practical issues.

The structure of the geometry course itself is also of great importance. This issue includes many specific questions, such as:

1) Correspondence of the school geometry course to the age characteristics of students. How should the geometry course be structured so that the presented material is accessible to both junior and senior schoolchildren; so that it contributes to the development of their personality?

2) How can studying the geometry course help implement the polytechnic education of students?

3) How to increase the scientific value of the course? This issue is closely related to finding out the possibility of increasing the rigor of the deductive presentation of the course, with geometric transformations and elements of Lobachevsky's geometry.

4) How to structure a geometry course to ensure the strength and systematicity of students' knowledge and create the best conditions for the development of their spatial imagination?

Other questions also arise here. Namely:

a) Should a geometry course be structured concentrically? What should be the general structure of the course?

b) What is the value of introducing students to axiomatic methods? How is it advisable to introduce this method?

c) A similar question arises about geometric transformations in a high school geometry course.

d) Is it necessary to introduce students to the elements of Lobachevsky's geometry and how to do it?

e) Is fusionism necessary and to what extent, or is it advisable to completely separate planimetry from stereometry?

f) Should trigonometric functions be used in a geometry course? What does this give?

And other questions.

At present, the school systematic course of geometry is divided into planimetry and stereometry. Such a division in some respects cannot but be recognized as convenient: it allows a poorly prepared student to study simpler questions of "flat" geometry at first, which facilitates the assimilation of the material and prepares for the study of more complex questions of the course - questions of stereometry. This division is to some extent due to the influence of tradition: "like Euclid".

The current clear division between planimetry and stereometry is one of the reasons for the weak development of students' spatial imagination.

It would seem that fusionism allows this shortcoming to be eliminated. However, if this is allowed, other methodological difficulties immediately arise. In particular, the entire geometry course would appear more complex to the student than with separate study of plane geometry and stereometry; it would be necessary to disperse their attention in two directions - facts on the plane and in space, which is unlikely to contribute to a clear understanding of the material being studied, most likely leading to confusion in the students' ideas, especially at the beginning of their studies, as a result of which the situation may turn out to be worse than it is now: students will not master either plane geometry or stereometry sufficiently well. It seems necessary to use the positive aspects of both directions in the interests of better development of students' spatial understanding

in the school geometry course. So, the problem of fusionism in geometry is ongoing. Its solution is now ripe.

The directions of fusionism in teaching geometry in secondary school can be the following:

- 1) Propaedeutics of a systematic geometry course (grades 5-6).
- 2) Interrelated study of the properties of plane and spatial figures in a systematic geometry course.
- 3) Solving planimetric problems on polyhedrons.
- 4) Analogies in planimetry and stereometry.

Thus, the idea of fusionism in geometry arose from the depths of geometry itself, was determined by the tasks of teaching one of the most figurative, living and practical sciences, especially in high school. We all know that childhood impressions are the strongest and most lasting impressions, they sometimes remain with a person for life. Therefore, the creation of bright, rather "difficult", developing textbooks, for example, on geometry, is necessary both at the initial stage of education, and in middle and senior grades, while we must not forget about the age and mental characteristics of children, their inclinations.

To identify fusionism in the study of geometric figures, we will form didactic blocks:

- 1) cube-square
- 2) parallelepiped-rectangle
- 3) pyramid-triangle
- 4) sphere-circle.

	For a plane	For a space
<i>Title</i>	Square	Cube
<i>Definition</i>	A rectangle in which all sides are equal	A rectangular parallelepiped with all sides equal
<i>Elements</i>	4 vertices, 4 sides, 2 diagonals	8 vertices, 6 faces, 12 edges, 4 diagonals
<i>Properties</i>	All angles of a square are right angles	All angles of a cube are right angles
	The diagonals of a square are equal, mutually perpendicular, and divided in half by the point of intersection.	The diagonals of a cube are equal and bisect at the point of intersection, but are not perpendicular to each other.
<i>Values</i>	$S=a^2$	$V=a^3$
<i>Title</i>	Rectangle	Rectangular parallelepiped
<i>Definition</i>	A rectangle is a parallelogram in which all angles are right angles.	A rectangular parallelepiped is a quadrangular prism, bases of which are rectangles.
<i>Elements</i>	4 vertices, 4 sides, 2 diagonals	8 vertices, 6 faces, 12 edges, 4 diagonals
<i>Properties</i>	The diagonals of a rectangle are equal and are divided in half by the intersection point	The diagonals of a rectangular parallelepiped are equal and, intersecting at one point, they

		are divided in half by the point of intersection
	Opposite sides of a rectangle are parallel and equal	Opposite faces of a rectangular parallelepiped are parallel and equal
Feature	If the diagonals of a parallelogram are equal, then the parallelogram is a rectangle.	If the diagonals of a quadrangular prism are equal, then it is a rectangular parallelepiped
Values	$S=ab$ multiplication of length and width	$V=abc$ multiplication of length, width and height
Title	Triangle	Tetrahedron
Definition	Three points that do not lie on the same line and are connected by segments	Four points in space that do not lie in the same plane and are connected by segments
Elements	Vertices, sides, height, median, bisector	Base, lateral faces, edges, height, apothem, apex
Values	$S=1/2ha$, where a is the base and h is the height drawn to it	$V=1/3 S(\text{base})h$, where h is the height drawn from the top to the base
Title	Circle	Sphere
Definition	A set of points on a plane that are equally distant from a given point and belong to the same plane	A set of points in space that are equally distant from a given point
Elements	Center of a circle, radius, diameter, chord, arc, sector. The concept of a circle	Sphere center, radius, chord, diameter, arc, sector. The concept of a sphere

Conclusion

Based on the data obtained during this and many other experiments, it can be stated that the fusionist approach to the presentation of the school geometry course contains a fairly high potential for the formation of cognitive interest in students and, consequently, their intellectual development. At the present stage, this approach is progressing, although there are still many difficulties in this regard. Accordingly, it can be concluded that conducting lessons using the idea of fusionism really contributes to improving geometric practice in students, increases interest in the subject and develops spatial imagination.

REFERENCES

1. Levitas G.G. Fusionism in school geometry// Mathematics at school, 1995, No. 6-P. 21-26.
2. Mitenev Yu.A. Use of information and communication technologies in teaching mathematics // Secondary vocational education. 2011. No. 6. P. 19-20.
3. Smirnova I.M. Ideas of fusionism in teaching school geometry// Mathematics (weekly supplement to the newspaper "First September"), No. 17, 1998.

4. Polat E.S. New pedagogical and information technologies in the education system. Moscow, 2009.
5. Pogorelov A.V. Geometry: Textbook for grades 7-11. Moscow: Education. 1991, p. 384.
6. Sharygin I.F. Geometry. 10-11 grades: Textbook. For secondary educational institutions. - 3rd ed. stereotype. - M.: 2001. - 208 p.